

Microbial indoor air quality and antibiotic resistance profile in the operating theatre of a university hospital (Bechar, Algeria)

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Summary

The emergence of novel or recurring pathogens and the multi-resistance of certain species towards antibiotics have led us to the surveillance of the microbial prevalence in the hospital's air. This study has deployed a methodological demonstration of the prominence of nosocomial pathogens in the University Hospital, Bechar (Algeria).

Airborne particles have been collected out of surgery and postoperative halls using the bio-collector "M-Air-T". After identifying the collected species, the antibiotic resistance of bacterial strains was evaluated.

The following pathogens were identified: *Staphylococcus* spp., with a dominance of 47.7%, in which we have found that 9% belong to the specific species of *S. aureus*, followed by 18.7% of *Enterobacter* spp., and noting an abundance of molds and yeast (*Aspergillus* spp., including *A. niger*, *Penicillium* spp., *Cladosporium* spp., *Alternaria* spp., *Rhizopus* spp. and *Mucor* spp.)

Antibiotic resistance pattern observed included: for *S. aureus* to oxacillin, amoxicillin and ampicillin, and for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Bacillus* spp. to beta-lactam family antibiotics. Factors influencing the risk of nosocomial infection have been found to vary depending on the type of surgery, age, length of preoperative hospitalization, duration of the operation and the number of people in the operating room. So, control of nosocomial infections requires, on one hand a proper isolation of the implicated pathogens in order to clearly outline this problem, and on the other hand awareness of resistance patterns for each of these pathogens. It is obvious that in addition to compliance with the basic rules of hygiene, the judicious use of drugs, the implementation of a policy of monitoring and a consortium between clinicians, microbiologists, and hospital pharmacists, remain essential to fight these hospital acquired infections.

Key words

Bio-collector; bacterial strains, M-Air-T, hygiene, nosocomial infections

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Introduction

Indoor air quality (IAQ) is an increasingly important issue for occupational and public health.¹

The microbial assessment of environments with heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems is even more important due to the high microbial biodiversity associated with high temperature and relative air humidity, favoring microbial growth.² This is particularly important for desert areas, where the temperature is above 40°C. A microbiological growth may occur in an HVAC system equipped with low-efficiency filters, humidifiers that use water recycling or in areas in which water condensation remains stagnant and large recirculation of the air is present.³

Sampling and analysis of airborne microorganisms in indoor air have received attention in recent years.⁴⁻⁶ In this context, of particular importance are pathogens with a propensity for antimicrobial resistance and a defined potential for human pathogenicity.

Bioaerosols are airborne particles that are either living (e.g. bacteria, fungi) or originate from living organisms that are ubiquitous, highly variable and complex and are natural or man-made in origin.⁷ In closed spaces with human presence and potential air mixing through ventilation systems, the generation of bioaerosols may pose significant risks.

Non-pathogenic microorganisms, especially airborne bacteria and fungi, may cause and trigger asthma or allergies among susceptible individuals and infections in persons with weak physical and immune background.⁸ Moreover, air can become a reservoir of germs causing nosocomial infections, especially in the most vulnerable patients in the operating theatre.

The present manuscript has therefore been designed to study the microbial air quality in the operating theatre by the detection and enumeration of a range of indicator bacteria and the antibiogram testing of microorganisms selected to highlight if resistant organisms are present.

Materials and methods

This study took place at the operating theatre of University Hospital, Bechar (Algeria). It is composed of several services including that of general surgery, where we took our samples. This service includes three operating theaters (Block A and B for scheduled operations, Block C for emergency operations) and a postoperative recovery room.

The microorganism is collected by M Air T® tester from Millipore (M Air T Kit, 50/60 Hz complete with carrying case, including M Air T Apparatus, ATAS PLR 01), to assess microbial air quality (airborne microorganism levels in critical areas). It uses a unique agar cassette design ensuring consistent nutrition capability of the agar surface. The cassette consists of a dark body to enhance contrast, and an integrated grid to partition the large surface into smaller areas for easier enumeration of colonies. The sieve of the tester contains close to 1000 micro-perforations. This minimizes colony overlapping.

Airborne pathogenic microorganisms in the surgical suites were collected for a volume of 1000 liters in less than 7 minutes and airflow rate at 140 L/min for the first 500 liters, then 180 L/min.

Totally 160 indoor air samples in the studied operating theaters (40 from Block A, 40 from Block B, 40 from Block C and 40 from postoperative recovery room) were collected directly after surgical intervention for five months, precisely from December 2017 to April 2018. The M-Air-T analyzer has been placed in several suspect locations (under the operating table when it comes to the block and under the beds when it comes to postoperative) to remove 1000 Liters of air.

We searched for microorganisms (total bacterial, specific bacterial and fungal counts) by using four culture medium: a plate count agar (PCA) used to enumerate total mesophilic aerobic organisms from which were incubated at 30°C for 48 hours; Mac Conkey agar for the isolation of Gram-negative bacteria, the collected bacteria were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours; Chapman agar selective medium for selecting the Staphylococci genera, followed by incubation at 37°C for 24 hours; Sabouraud agar for the isolation of general fungi. The Petri dishes were incubated for 5 days at 25°C. All plates were labeled by the number of the sample, the date, and site of the sampling, and then stored at 4°C during transportation to the laboratory.

After incubation, an enumeration to express as a colony-forming unit per cubic meter (CFU/m³) was necessary for a statistical interpretation.

The identification by macroscopic examination of colonies was followed by a microscopic identification using Gram-stain. The second step is based on micro-

scopic examination and biochemical identification through the classical and miniaturized galleries (IMVIC, oxidase test, Respiratory type and API 20E (BioMérieux, France) for *Enterobacterales* family; staphylocoagulase, Deoxyribonuclease (DNase) test, catalase test and Mannitol Motility Test for *S. aureus*; search of pyocyanin and pyoverdine production, oxidase test and Mannitol Motility for *P. aeruginosa*; sporulation test, penicillin susceptibility, lecithinase and gelatinase productions for *Bacillus*; microculture method and single-spore isolates for fungi).

Antibiotic susceptibility testing was determined using the disk diffusion method on Muller-Hinton agar as described by the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards (NCCLS, 2013).¹³ The antibiotics used are: ampicillin, cefoxitin, cefazolin, gentamicin, imipenem, chloramphenicol, ofloxacin, and cefotaxime tested for *Enterobacterales*; penicillin, oxacillin, vancomycin, fosfomicin, fusidic acid, erythromycin, amikacin, and gentamicin for *Staphylococcus* spp.; and finally, gentamicin, imipenem, chloramphenicol, vancomycin, Tetracyclin for *Bacillus* spp.

Statistical analysis

Results were expressed as mean and standard deviation (SD). Statistical analyses were determined using Excel 2007.

Results

Through the 40 samples taken for each room (Block A, B, C, and a postoperative recovery room) at the level of general surgery services, various bacterial and fungal isolates were observed.

The values of bacterial and fungal contamination detected in the studied wards were compared with categories of contamination indicated in NF S90-351 (2013).¹⁰

The results obtained by the detection of total flora on the PCA medium show that there is qualitative and quantitative variability between the different samples taken.

The results of the macroscopic and microscopic study of isolated colonies after culture gave us a differentiation in the cultural aspects and the microscopic characters of the germs incriminated in several infections.

The isolated Gram-negative bacilli and Gram-positive cocci, their proportions, and their distribution in the different sampled areas are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

A total of air samples collected from the different rooms showed that the postoperative room revealed a high level of air contamination reaching on average 15.4±18.98 CFU/m³ for bacteria and 5.9±2.68 CFU/m³

Table 1 Number of bacterial and fungal isolates from air of operating theaters.

	Number of colony-forming units (CFU m ⁻³ air)			
	Block A Mean ± SD	Block B Mean ± SD	Block C Mean ± SD	Postoperative recovery room Mean ± SD
Bacteria 30°C	05±3.97	10.9±10.73	7.1±8.25	15.4±18.98
Bacteria 37°C	5.35±8.69	7.2±8.84	5.85±4.69	12.15±8.43
Fungi 25°C	4.2±3.01	4.4±2.83	6.3±3.30	5.9±2.68

SD: standard deviation

Table 2 Number of a bacterial community isolates from studied air samples.

Genera	Number	Percentage
Gram negative n= 43 (40.2%)		
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	5	4.7%
<i>Enterobacter</i> spp.	20	18.7%
<i>Citrobacter</i> spp.	5	4.7%
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	13	12.1%
Gram-positive n= 64 (59.8%)		
<i>Bacillus</i> spp.	13	12.1%
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	51	47.7%
Total	107	

Table 3 Number of fungi isolates from studied air samples.

Genera	Number	Percentage
<i>Aspergillus</i> spp.	58	51.3%
<i>A. niger</i>	5	4.4%
<i>Cladosporium</i> spp.	15	13.3%
<i>Penicillium</i> spp.	21	18.6%
<i>Alternaria</i> spp.	9	08%
<i>Mucorales (Rhizopus & Mucor)</i>	5	4.4%
Total	n=113	100(%)

for fungi. The microbial load of the other operating room does not exceed mean bacterial and fungal counts of (10.9 ± 10.73 CFU/m³ and 6.3 ± 3.30 CFU/m³) respectively.

The isolated organisms consisted of *Bacillus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Enterobacteriales* and *Pseudomonas* spp. *Staphylococcus* strains predominate in the different rooms with 47.7% of all pathogens collected. Analysis of the results of the total fungal flora indicated the presence of: *Aspergillus* spp., *Penicillium* spp., *Cladosporium* spp., *Alternaria* spp., *Rhizopus* spp. and *Mucor* spp.), with the predominance of *Aspergillus* spp., reaching 51.3% of all detected mycoflora, as shown in Table 3. The maximum average of total mycoflora appeared in Block C (6.3 ± 3.30 CFU m⁻³ air), while the mean was 4.2 ± 3.01 and 4.4 ± 2.83 CFU m⁻³ air for Block A and B respectively. (Table 1).

Susceptibility results showed resistance of *E. coli*, *Enterobacter* spp., *Citrobacter* spp. to ampicillin, cefoxitin and cefotaxime. However, imipenem was active against all tested strains, while all strains were susceptible to gentamicin, ofloxacin, amikacin, as shown in Table 4.

Discussion

Numerous studies published during the past 10–15 years have produced rather solid scientific evidence that indoor aerosol particles, especially in the respirable fraction, are associated with health effects. Viable bioaerosol particles, including viruses, bacteria, and fungi, have been associated with respiratory allergies and asthma and have been linked to the airborne transmission of various infections.³

Table 4 Susceptibility results of bacterial isolates.

Antibiotics	Bacterial isolates from air of operating theaters					
	<i>E. coli</i> n=5 D	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp n=51 D	<i>Enterobacter</i> spp n=20 D	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> n=13 D	<i>Citrobacter</i> spp n=5 D	<i>Bacillus</i> spp n=13 D
Ampicillin	8-9	–	18-20	–	16-17	–
Cefoxitin	27-28	21-23	18-22	–	20-22	–
Cefazolin	–	–	–	12-16	–	–
Gentamicin	26-27	22-26	20-25	25-31	20-22	26-30
Imipenem	28-30	–	23-29	30-36	23-26	28-32
chloramphenicol	25-27	–	20-23	–	19-22	18-19
Ofloxacin	20-21	–	21-25	22-27	25-27	–
Cefotaxime	19-21	–	22-27	25-30	24-25	–
Penicillin	–	20-24	–	–	–	–
Oxacillin	–	15-20	–	–	–	–
Vancomycin	–	–	–	–	–	25-29
Fosfomycin	17-19	–	21-25	–	21-23	–
Fusidic acid	–	10-14	–	–	–	–
Erythromycin	–	09-15	–	–	–	–
Amikacin	20-23	22-25	20-25	17-20	26-29	–
Tetracyclin	–	–	–	–	–	25-28

D: Diameter of inhibition zones (mm), n: Number of bacteria.

It has been estimated by several authors that 10 to 20% of endemic nosocomial infections are airborne. This estimate includes airborne interhuman transmissions.^{2,4} Surgical site infections account for 14% to 17% of all hospital acquired infections and 38% of nosocomial infections in surgical patients.¹¹

Sampling is an essential phase of the control procedure, indeed, the analytical means and skills are useless if the samples are not representative of the contamination to be quantified. The bio-collector (M-Air-T) has collection efficiency even when the contaminant is rare. Moreover, by obtaining representative and reliable results, this technology has a real advantage in the field.

The evaluation of air quality in a health facility for microbiological parameters is highly dependent on significant variations depending on seasons of the day, the time, the nature of patient contamination and their health conditions. It has been noticed that almost all strains are common between services, it's perhaps due to movements of the personnel, sick people and especially the lack of hygiene, since the services are complementary and the patient has to go through a whole routine to arrive at his service of stay.

The requirements relating to the control of airborne contamination, the average does not exceed 10 CFU/m³ and 1 CFU/m³ for bacteria and fungi respectively.¹⁰ According to these standards, during our study at the different rooms of the operating theatre, the results found show that international standards are not met, concerning the high load of air bacteria, most of them are bacteria indicative of a lack of hygiene. However, it appears that *Staphylococcus* spp. is the most common pathogen in both rooms of the operating theater with a rate of 47.7%, while *Aspergillus* spp. With 51.3% predominate in fungal isolates.

This charge causes a risk of respiratory infection because these infectious agents can be transported as airborne particles or droplets, most infections are due to particles inhalation from 1 to 5 micron.¹² Corne et al.,¹³ have shown that several strains of *S. aureus* from pneumonia and bronchitis are derived from the nasal cavity, potentiating a respiratory spread of these pathogens.

The abundance of the fungal flora represented for the most part by *Aspergillus* spp. raises the possibility of allergy and mycoses induction (aspergillosis). *Aspergillus* spp. in volumetric air samples is the cause of nosocomial epidemics.¹⁴ Moreover isolation of *Penicillium* spp. and *Cladosporium* spp. airborne fungi increases the risk of spreading infectious diseases.⁶ Further, infectious particles depend on the frequency of respiratory activity, type, site of infection and pathogens load.¹⁵ According to the results found in our study, it can be said that laminar air flow is insufficient to keep sterile air at the operating theatre.¹⁶

The isolated germs had some resistance to antibiotics. Specifically, *E. coli*, *Enterobacter* spp., *Citrobacter* spp., and *Staphylococcus* spp were resistant to penicillin, oxacillin, ampicillin, and erythromycin while, our results concerning other types of antibiotics, such as amikacin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, imipenem, and fosfomycin presented a high activity, consistent results with those reported by Muratani and Matsu-moto.¹⁷

In conclusion, this study revealed high microbial contamination in the operating room for the various samples taken. The special microbiological controls of air quality are a fundamental step in the mastery and prevention of environmental risks, they are essential to verify the proper functioning of air treatment facilities or to detect possible drifts to preventively way.

Περίληψη

Μελέτη μικροβιακού φορτίου και αντοχής των απομονούμενων μικροβίων του αέρα χειρουργικής αίθουσας πανεπιστημιακού νοσοκομείου (Bechar, Αλγερία)

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Η απομόνωση παθογόνων στο νοσοκομειακό περιβάλλον, σε συνδυασμό με την πολυαντοχή ορισμένων από αυτά στα αντιβιοτικά έχουν οδηγήσει στην επιτήρηση του αέρα σε νοσοκομειακούς χώρους όπως κυρίως οι χειρουργικές αίθουσες. Η παρούσα μελέτη είχε ως σκοπό την απομόνωση, ταυτοποίηση και έλεγχο ευαισθησίας μικροοργανισμών που απομονώθηκαν από τον έλεγχο αέρα στις χειρουργικές αίθουσες του Πανεπιστημιακού Νοσοκομείου στο Bechar της Αλγερίας. Ο έλεγχος του αέρα στις αίθουσες χειρουργείου έγινε με τη χρήση του συλλέκτη αέρα "M-Air-T". Η ταυτοποίηση των απομονούμενων μικροοργανισμών έδειξε την ύπαρξη των ακόλουθων γενών: *Staphylococcus* spp., σε ποσοστό 47,7% (9% αυτών ταυτοποιήθηκαν ως *S. aureus*), *Enterobacter* spp. σε ποσοστό 18,7%, καθώς και ποικιλία υφομυκήτων (*Aspergillus* spp., συμπεριλαμβανομένου *A. niger*, *Penicillium* spp., *Cladosporium* spp., *Alternaria* spp., *Rhizopus* spp. και *Mucor* spp.). Ο έλεγχος ευαισθησίας έδειξε αντοχή του *S. aureus* σε οξακιλλίνη, αμοξικιλίνη και αμπικιλίνη, ενώ τα στελέχη *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* και *Bacillus* spp. παρουσίασαν αντοχή στα β-λακταμικά αντιβιοτικά.

Οι παράγοντες που επηρεάζουν τον κίνδυνο νοσοκομειακής λοίμωξης έχουν βρεθεί ότι ποικίλλουν ανάλογα με τον τύπο της χειρουργικής επέμβασης, την ηλικία του ασθενούς, τη διάρκεια της προεγχειρητικής νοσηλείας, τη διάρκεια της επέμβασης και τον αριθμό των ατόμων στο χειρουργείο. Ο έλεγχος των νοσοκομειακών λοιμώξεων απαιτεί, αφενός, απομόνωση των υπεύθυνων μικροβίων προκειμένου να προσδιοριστεί με σαφήνεια το πρόβλημα, και από την άλλη καλή γνώση της ευαισθησίας τους στα συνήθη χρησιμοποιούμενα αντιβιοτικά. Είναι προφανές ότι εκτός από τη συμμόρφωση με τους βασικούς κανόνες υγιεινής, η συνετή χρήση των αντιβιοτικών, η εφαρμογή πολιτικής χρήσης τους και κυρίως η συνεργασία μεταξύ κλινικών, εργαστηριακών γιατρών και κλινικών φαρμακοποιών, είναι ουσιαστικής σημασίας για τον έλεγχο των νοσοκομειακών λοιμώξεων.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

έλεγχος αέρα, M-Air-T συλλέκτης αέρα, νοσοκομειακές λοιμώξεις

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